

PRINCIPLE OF MEASUREMENT GEOMETRIC ACCURACY OF MACHINE TOOLS

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References

- Soori, M., Arezoo, B. and Habibi, M., 2013. Dimensional and geometrical errors of three-axis CNC milling machines in a virtual machining system. *Computer-Aided Design*, 45(11), pp.1306-1313.